

Original Article

Moldovan scientific conferences: Predatory or merely misguided?

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Received: 21 Feb 2025

Accepted: 7 May 2025

Published: 14 Jul 2025

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available upon request from the corresponding author.

Acknowledgements

This study was conducted within the research project titled 'The phenomenon of publishing in pseudoscientific predatory editions in the academic community of the Republic of Moldova'.

Declaration of Interests

The author has no conflicts of interest to declare.

Funding

This study has been funded by the National Agency for Research and Development of the Republic of Moldova (ref: 24.80012.0807.14SE)..

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Citation

Cuciureanu G. Moldovan scientific conferences: Predatory or merely misguided? *Eur Sci Ed.* 2025;51:e150991.

<https://doi.org/10.3897/ese.2025.e150991>

Abstract

Background: Predatory conferences vary greatly in their format, scale, and organization and adversely affect researchers from less developed countries the most. Although ways to identify such conferences continue to be refined, their organizers are often a step ahead and strive to be increasingly sophisticated. One effective way of detecting whether a given conference is predatory is to submit a nonsensical manuscript and monitor its fate.

Objective: To examine the extent to which scientific conferences organized by institutions in Moldova match the established markers of predatory conferences.

Methods: A manuscript authored by a fictitious individual was submitted to 16 scientific conferences. The manuscript included passages copied verbatim from other sources and introduced a fabricated and absurd indicator for evaluating science, namely the Timmy Index (named after the author's dog). The conferences were subsequently matched against established markers for predatory conferences.

Results: Of the 16 conferences, 14 accepted the manuscript; 9 issued a certificate of attendance; and 12 published the article in their proceedings, although none of the 16 charged any participation or publication fees.

Conclusions: Pseudoscientific conferences are deeply embedded in the academic community of Moldova. The operational model employed by these conferences fosters a publication culture among local researchers that makes it acceptable to submit manuscripts to predatory journals and conferences, prioritizing rapid publishing for a fee and without proper peer review or an actual presentation at a conference.

Keywords: Moldova, nonsensical research paper, predatory conferences, predatory publishing

Introduction

Scientific conferences play a crucial role in disseminating and discussing research findings, facilitating knowledge exchange, and strengthening the academic community. However, these benefits are compromised when the purpose of organizing conferences strays from academic considerations, and such conferences are commonly referred to as 'predatory' conferences.

Literature on predatory *conferences* is limited, especially when compared to that on predatory *journals*; however, the two modes share a number of similar features, which are often highlighted.¹ The reason for limited research on predatory conferences probably lies in the difficulty in distinguishing them from legitimate conferences.² However, a number of significant studies have addressed the specifics and the impact of predatory conferences.^{3–10} Also, lists of predatory conferences (Kscien list, for example) and of predatory publishers (Predatory Publisher list, for example) have been compiled.

Predatory conferences vary significantly in their format, scale, and organization, and the absence of universally recognized ways to identify them aggravates the threat.¹¹ Some researchers argue that a binary classification of conferences – as either good or bad – is not feasible; instead, they propose a spectrum of conferences: fraudulent, deceptive, unacceptably low quality, low quality, low quality but promising, questionable quality, and high quality.⁹ Beall¹² proposed 45 criteria for identifying predatory conferences, and McCrostie⁷ suggested that for a conference to be classified as predatory, it must meet three criteria: (1) the organizer conducts low-quality academic meetings primarily for financial gain; (2) the peer review process is either ineffective or absent; and (3) the organizer employs deceit. Asadi et al⁶ identified 16 signs of fake or bogus

conferences, and Pecorari² established five areas for assessing the legitimacy of a conference (selectivity, footprint, the nature of the transaction, credibility, and substance) and formulated 16 questions to guide researchers in deciding whether to submit a paper to a conference. The InterAcademy Partnership Report synthesizes the common features of predatory conferences and outlines typical descriptors for three categories: fake and deceptive conferences, unacceptably low-quality conferences, and low-quality conferences.⁹ The characteristics of predatory conferences have also been delineated by Beshyah,¹³ Memon and Azim,¹⁴ Pawar,¹⁵ and Eaton.¹⁶ Regardless of how the features of predatory conferences are framed and the number of such features, researchers converge on the idea, which I share, that predatory conferences are events organized for financial gain at the expense of the quality of papers presented and published.

Although predatory conferences are attended by authors from prestigious universities, it appears that, as with predatory journals, the individuals affected most by such conferences are early-career researchers and those from less developed countries.^{5,9,17,18} Predatory conference publishing has deeply infiltrated the Moldovan scientific community. A matter of even greater concern is the fact that many university professors, PhD supervisors, and other academics who influence the behaviour of young researchers have also attended such conferences and have published in predatory journals.¹⁹

Although many criteria for identifying predatory publishing have been established, the practices associated with predatory conferences are becoming increasingly sophisticated, making it more challenging to detect them.^{9,20} One of the methods employed in studies on predatory conferences involves submitting nonsensical or intentionally

flawed manuscripts to such conferences. This approach tests the rigour of their review process and helps to determine whether a given conference is fake or bogus.⁶

Many of the studies that use the above method rely on a computer program called SCIGen to generate the nonsensical submissions.²¹ Mathias Uslar's article 'A Case for Lamport Clocks' was accepted at the IPSI-2005 Venice conference,²² and the article 'Towards the Simulation of E-commerce', by the fictional author Herbert Schlangemann, was accepted at the 2008 International Conference, co-sponsored by the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE).²³ A French researcher demonstrated that over 30 conference proceedings published between 2008 and 2013 included articles generated by computer programs. Consequently, the publishers Springer and IEEE removed more than 120 papers from their subscription services for this reason.²¹

Cases of acceptance of such 'scientific' papers have been documented across various scientific fields and geographical regions. A paper by a fictional Turkish author was accepted in 2007 at a WASET (World Academy of Science, Engineering and Technology) conference.²⁴ Another notable instance involves the Indian author Navin Kabra, who in 2013 submitted a bogus paper, titled 'Use of Cloud-computing and Social Media to Determine Box Office Performance', to the ICRIEST-AICEEMCS international conference. Despite the paper referencing the 1970s Bollywood film *Sholay*, the submission was accepted.²⁵ In a separate case, Diane Pecorari, a researcher from Hong Kong, submitted ten fake abstracts in different subject areas under pseudonyms to conferences organized by 10 organizations between 2019 and 2020. Although the abstracts were nonsensical (for example, one described a study of stress on building foundations that involved placing a gorilla on top of a

skyscraper and causing a cyclone to pick up a house and drop it on a yellow brick road), she received 97 notifications of acceptance, with seven organizations accepting all 10 abstracts.²

Similar cases related to Moldovan science have also been examined. Almost all Moldovan scientific journals in the field of law accepted for publication an article by a PhD student in 2016/17 despite the fact that it reproduced in its entirety the content of an article published earlier in one of those very journals.²⁶ The article 'Aspects of Virtual Scientific Authorship in Conditions of Moral and Legal Nihilism', submitted by a fictional author from Moldova, was published abroad in the proceedings of a fake conference and in a journal. Although the article described predatory practices and demonstrated that the very conference to which the article had been submitted was predatory, it was accepted for publication within 30 minutes of submission and a certificate of attendance was issued within 30 minutes of paying the required fee.²⁷

It is against this background that the present study sought to examine, through an experimental approach, the extent to which scientific conferences either organized by institutions in Moldova or those in which Moldovan institutions participate reflect the established signs of predatory conferences.

Methods

Procedure

The present research took the form of a large case study. A pseudoscientific manuscript authored by a fictitious author, Vladimir Mocan, was submitted to multiple scientific conferences organized by institutions in Moldova. The author registered for all the selected conferences as Vladimir Mocan, and the manuscript was adapted where necessary

to meet the technical requirements of a given conference. The conferences were also matched against the criteria for considering a given conference as predatory, as synthesized in the project ‘The phenomenon of publishing in pseudoscientific predatory editions in the academic community of the Republic of Moldova’ (PSEUDO-MD). The study followed the recommendations by Adam Larson and Matan Shelomi, namely that such sting operations against predatory publishing should include a peer review red-flags in the paper that identify it beyond reasonable doubt as a spurious paper; make the results of successful sting operations public; and should involve neither any benefit to the predatory publisher nor any cost to the author.²⁸

Manuscript preparation

The general content of the manuscript was taken from the report ‘What should research assessment reform aim to deliver and how to get there?’, published in December 2022 by Science|Business. This report advocates for reforms in research assessment and addresses one of the reasons for the rise of predatory publishing, namely the misuse of bibliometric indicators and the adoption of the ‘publish or perish’ principle. The study concludes that Moldova should leverage international experience and introduce new indicators that are better at reflecting the quality of research, ensuring transparency, and aligning with the purpose of assessment. The spurious manuscript proposed an absurd index, the Timmy Index, named after the author’s dog. The index quantifies the amount, in tonnes, of bones that could be bought with the annual income of a researcher. The manuscript applied the index to university rectors and directors of research institutions and showed figures displaying the ranking of universities and research institutes by their Timmy Index. The manuscript concluded that the ‘Index excellently reflects the scientific

performance of the heads of the institutions and of the institutions themselves, because in a knowledge society, it is evident that the more knowledge an organization produces, the higher the remuneration of its leaders this way, it is unnecessary to use complex, numerous indicators, which have many shortcomings; with only the Timmy Index, we can, in ‘one shot’, solve multiple problems, confirming once again that everything simple is brilliant!’ The bibliography appended to the manuscript was sourced from the paper ‘New Approaches in Research Assessment—From Bibliometrics to Goals-oriented Approaches: The Case of Researchers’ assessment for hiring and career development in Romania’ (*Europolity* 15 (2), 2020). The title chosen for the spurious manuscript was ‘A New Approach to Science Evaluation: Using the Timmy Index’.

Selection of conferences

The conferences for manuscript submission were selected from the national platform for scientific events (conferinte.stiu.md). In selecting, the preferred conferences were those with a generalist theme (representing multiple fields of science), with many participants, organized annually by the most important universities in Moldova. These criteria helped to ensure that the selected conferences were fairly good representatives of scientific events in Moldova. This selection resulted in 14 conferences, all hosted by large Moldovan universities. Participation in the Moldovan conferences led to invitations to two more, organized abroad (in Ukraine and Turkey). Most of the conferences took place in 2023; however, two were chosen for attendance in 2024 to check whether the organizers would notice the repetition of the openly accessible paper within a year. These two events were of particular interest: one was the largest national event organized by Moldova’s largest university, and the other

was organized in a Western European country but by a Turkish institution, raising suspicions, and was included in the study although it did not meet the condition that the conferences should be those organized by Moldovan institutions.

Data

The information gathered during registration and correspondence with the organizers of conferences was systematically organized and then analyzed. Data collection for matching the features of the conferences against the criteria for determining whether a conference should be considered predatory involved interactions with conference organizers, using the official websites of the conferences, and the National Platform of Scientific Events.

Ethics

This study did not involve human participants as subjects. As to the ethical considerations related to the relationships with the organizations and individuals involved in organizing these conferences, the author of the study shares the view of other researchers (for example, Pecorari²): Given the violations of scientific ethics and publishing standards, the potential harm to the organizations is outweighed by the damage they cause and the possible benefits from the findings of the study.

Results and Discussion

Of the 16 conferences to which manuscripts were submitted for participation and for publication in conference proceedings, only 2 did not accept the submissions (Table 1). The analysis of the conferences in light of the 12 criteria for labelling a conference as predatory, developed in the framework of the PSEUDO-MD project, is presented here for each of those criteria.

Low-quality websites and published materials

Only four conferences had dedicated websites (Conferences 7, 8, 9, and 10 in Table 1). For the other conferences, information was typically found on the organizers' web pages, which often contained limited details, primarily focusing on technical details such as deadlines and formatting requirements for submissions. For instance, the organizer's website for Conference 13 provided only a brief announcement of the event, making it unclear whether proceedings were published. In this case, the details were dispersed across various sites, which may serve as a strategy to obscure the information. In contrast, the official websites for Conferences 2 and 11 featured a dedicated section for scientific events, offering more structured information (conference agenda, edited volumes, video recordings, etc.) than that offered by the others. Additionally, all conferences held in Moldova were registered on the National Platform for Scientific Events, which provided detailed information about each event, thereby enhancing the transparency and quality of event-related information.

Attractive and generic names and mimicry

All the conference names included the term 'international' and indicated their traditional status. Two events were labelled 'Congresses'. Most of the events had titles that were fairly broad, not particularly specific. Although some conferences featured narrowly focused titles (such as the Knowledge Economy, Public Administration, Ethics, Statistics, and IT in Economics), six featured extremely broad themes such as 'Science, Education, Culture', 'Tradition and Innovation in Scientific Research', and 'Integration through Research and Innovation'. Particularly noteworthy was the 'Mediterranean Scientific Research Congress', a name that, combined

Table 1. Information about conferences at which the Timmy Index was submitted

No.	Conference title	Date (2023 unless stated otherwise)	Location (all in Moldova except 7 and 13) and link to organizing institution	Partners from abroad (number of partners or countries)	Scientific committee (number of members or countries)	Proceedings (link)	Mocan's participation	
							Published paper (link)	Participation certificate
1	International Scientific-Practical Conference on Science, Education, Culture, 13th edn (edition)	10 February	Comrat Institution	No	Yes, 38 / 8	Yes - 1, 2, 3	Yes	Yes
2	The Moldavian-Polish-Romanian International Scientific Congress on Education, Policies and Society	13-15 March	Chişinău Institution	No	Yes, 24 / 4	Yes	No	Yes
3	International Conference on EU: Building links to Eastern Partnership countries	15-16 March	Chişinău Institution	No	Yes, 9 / 2	Yes - 1, 2	Yes	Yes
4	International Conference on Management Strategies and Policies in the Contemporary Economy, 8th edn	24-25 March	Chişinău Institution	Yes, 4 / 3	Yes, 22 / 7	Yes	Yes	No
5	International Conference on Research, Development and Innovation from the perspective of Global Ethics, 4th edn	12 May	Chişinău Institution	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
6	International Scientific-Practical Conference on Theory and practice of public administration, 27th edn	19 May	Chişinău Institution	No	Yes, 14 / 5	Yes	Yes	No
7	International Scientific-Practical Conference on Statistical methods and information technologies for the analysis of socio-economic development, 23th edn	1 June	Khmelnytskyi, Ukraine Institution	Yes, 4 / 2 (2 from Moldova)	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
8	International Scientific Conference on Perspectives and problems of integration in the European area of research and education, 10th edn	7 June	Cahul Institution	Yes, 4 / 2	Yes, 30 / 3	Yes - 1, 2	Yes	Yes
9	International Scientific-Professional Conference on Economic Development and Research, 2th edn	21-23 June	Chişinău Institution	Yes, 11 / 6	Yes, 31 / 6	Yes	Yes	Yes
10	International Scientific Conference on Competitiveness and Innovation in the Knowledge Economy, 27th edn	22-23 September	Chişinău Institution	Yes, 10 / 4	Yes, 52 / 5	Yes, IR	Yes	No
11	International Scientific Conference on Higher Education: traditions, values, perspectives, 2th edn	28-29 September	Chişinău Institution	No	Yes, 20 / 5	Yes	No	Yes
12	Scientific Conference with international participation on Tradition and Innovation in Scientific Research, 12th edn	6-7 October	Bălţi Institution	No	Yes, 7 / 1	Yes	Yes	Yes
13	International Mediterranean Scientific Research Congress, 6th edn	13-15 August 2024	Rome, Italy Institution	No	Yes, 20 / 11	Yes - 1, 2	Yes	No

(Continued)

Table 1. Information about conferences at which the Timmy Index was submitted (Continued)

No.	Conference title	Date (2023 unless stated otherwise)	Location (all in Moldova except 7 and 13) and link to organizing institution	Partners from abroad (number of partners or countries)	Scientific committee (numbers of members or countries)	Proceedings (link)	Mocan's participation	
							Published paper (link)	Participation certificate
14	National Scientific Conference with international participation on Integration Through Research and Innovation, 11th edn	7–8 November 2024	Chişinău Institution	No	Yes, 68 / 6	Yes – 1, 2, 3, 4	Yes	No
15	International Scientific-Practical Conference on Economic Growth in the Conditions of the Globalization, 17th edn	12 October	Chişinău Institution	No	Yes, 53 / 10	Yes – 1, 2, 3	No	No
16	International Scientific Conference on Modern Paradigms in the Development of the National and World Economy, 16th edn	6–7 October	Chişinău Institution	No	Yes, 30 / 7	Yes	No	No

1/ Conferences 1–14, all of which accepted the submitted manuscript, are listed in chronological order; conferences 15 and 16 did not accept the manuscript.

2/ Most conferences held in Moldova provided a link to the conference on the national platform and an evidence sheet on the national platform; conferences 7 and 13 provided neither; and Conference 16 provided only the link.

with the location (Rome), seemingly aimed to attract participants by suggesting that it was a unique scientific event for the Mediterranean region. However, an analysis of the participants' profiles and publications from these conferences revealed that the names did not match the declared geographical scope. However, we did not find titles that were near-identical to those of recognized and reputable journals or conferences worldwide so as to suggest mimicry, a well-known tactic for attracting authors by misleading them.

Rapid acceptance and publication

For these conferences, rapid acceptance of abstracts was primarily aimed at confirming the names of participants in the conference programme. Full articles, intended for publication in the conference proceedings, were sometimes accepted upon submission of the manuscript, either before the event took place or shortly afterwards. The time frame for acceptance was generally short, but often the author received no intimation of acceptance and knew of it only on seeing the paper in the published proceedings. The acceptance process did not involve any discussion on the quality of the content, feedback on text, or suggestions for revisions. For example, at Conference 1, the deadline for registration and submission of extended abstracts was 15 January 2023. The (fictitious) author submitted the registration form only on 21 January and the manuscript on 3 February. Yet, a communication confirming acceptance of the manuscript was received the same day, and the conference agenda, which featured the fictional author, was distributed by 8 February (the event was scheduled for 19 February). On 14 February, a certificate of participation was issued, and subsequently the article was published in the conference proceedings without any further contact or discussion with the organizers.

Aggressive recruitment of authors and scientific committee members

No evidence of aggressive recruitment policies was found, with the possible exception of Conference 13; this took the form of follow-up invitations to participate in other events organized by the same entity. Additionally, invitations were sent for the next edition of the event by the organizers of some of the conferences held in 2023; however, these invitations did not appear to be aggressively worded.

Broad scientific fields (multidisciplinarity)

Six conferences featured themes so broad as to encompass nearly all scientific fields. One of these conferences (13) presented the most diverse range of topics, including those from natural, engineering, agricultural, socio-human, and even medical sciences. Four of the conferences were the main scientific events of the year for four generalist universities in Moldova (conferences 1, 8, 12, and 14), and three conferences served as the main scientific events for the more specialized universities (conferences 9, 10, and 11); however, the themes of these conferences extended beyond their institutions' specializations, probably to allow collaborators from other fields to participate as well. Multidisciplinarity, a hallmark of predatory conferences,^{2,6,16} makes peer review particularly difficult and complicates the fulfilment of the conference's mission. This challenge is particularly evident if the specific section or theme attracts only a few participants, which limits any meaningful academic discussion and the validation of results. For example, at Conference 13, the programme indicated sessions featuring 5–7 presentations; however, the topics often lacked homogeneity. In one instance, the moderator of a session – focused on materials science and engineering – held a PhD in Law from Moldova.

Unjustified publication fees, out of proportion to the services offered

Excessive fees are a common characteristic of predatory publishers,^{7,29} particularly because they operate under an open-access model. However, none of the analysed conferences charged a fee for attendance or for publication in their proceedings. Therefore, the primary motive for organizing these conferences by higher education institutions appears to be to help their staff in fulfilling the requirements of publications, project deliverables, and academic promotion.

Suspiciously high publication frequency

The analysed conferences were held annually, and their proceedings were published once a year. However, for some conferences, the number of published papers significantly exceeded the number of talks delivered at those events. Furthermore, the organizers of these conferences also arranged numerous other events. For example, the webpage featuring the events organized by the host of Conference 13 lists various congresses and conferences, each in a numbered series and held in different cities (Paris, New York, London, Houston, etc.). This practice is characteristic of predatory publishers, who often hold conferences in cities that are popular tourist destinations. Moldovan universities frequently organize multiple conferences on the same theme within a short time frame, which does not contribute to enhancing the quality of the papers and may result in the presentation of research that lacks scientific novelty. For instance, the organizer of Conference 14, during the same approximate period as this traditional event covering virtually all scientific fields in 2023, also held separate scientific events in specific disciplines, such as an international scientific conference in education sciences and another in economic sciences. Moreover, in the field of law and between September and December

2023 alone, the organizer conducted as many as 17 scientific events.³⁰

Lack of coverage by major databases and false bibliometrics

Although indexing by major databases and the resultant bibliometrics are applicable more to scientific journals than to scientific conferences, we also sought such details for the analysed conferences. Proceedings from the 14 Moldovan conferences are indexed in the National Bibliometric Instrument but not in international databases. However, there was no evidence of false claims of being thus indexed.

Presence in lists of predatory sources

None of the conferences appeared in the lists of predatory publishers or events (such as the Kscien list, Beall's List or Predatory Journals' Lists), nor did we find any negative comments from the scientific community online. However, it is important to note that such lists often do not include predatory publications based in Eastern Europe, such as 'InterConf', which was previously the most popular organizer of predatory conferences for researchers from Moldova.²⁷

Dysfunctional scientific committees, often presented with false information

With the exception of Conference 7, all the other conferences indicated the presence of a scientific committee. The number of committee members varied from 7 to 68, as did their affiliations and countries. In some instances, well-known national or international names were included to enhance prestige and potentially to add an international dimension to the conference. For example, Conferences 1 and 10 each included members from eight countries. In contrast, Conference 8 comprised 30 members, drawn from only three countries, among whom eight were university rectors, three were university vice-rectors, one was

the president of an academy of sciences, and two were directors of research institutes (as given in the conference agenda). It is noteworthy that many prominent figures have no publications in conference proceedings.

There is no reason or evidence to doubt that the individuals, both domestic and international, who were part of the scientific committees for the conferences were not aware of this fact, as is often the case with predatory conferences.^{15,31} However, the extent of their claimed participation in different conference-related activities and the quality of the published conference proceedings suggest that these individuals had not contributed materially either to the organization of the conference or to the review of manuscripts.

Non-adherence to standards of scientific conferences or published articles

The proper organization of a conference requires the presentation of research communications and discussions on the topics addressed. The fictitious author, Mocan, was unable to present his contribution at any of the conferences in person; however, he nevertheless received a certificate of participation for nine conferences (Table 1). Furthermore, the organizers saw nothing wrong in publishing in the conference proceedings a paper that had not been presented at the event. For example, in Conference 2, during registration, participants had the option to either present their work or publish it without attending the conference. In Conference 4, the session that included the fictitious author listed 38 presentations; however, only six of these were delivered during the conference.

The acceptance of a paper with passages copied from another source highlighted the absence of plagiarism policies or checks and the lack of mechanisms for retracting articles at these conferences. All proceedings from the conferences included on Moldova's national

platform were indexed in the National Bibliometric Instrument, which has established digital preservation policies. However, the two conferences held outside Moldova raise significant concerns regarding archiving and digital preservation practices. For Conference 7, the proceedings were stored on Google Drive, and for Conference 13, the proceedings were challenging to locate: they were hosted on a website different from the conference website and were available only as a single file in PDF, lacking any search and filtering options.

Additional deviations from best practices for scientific conferences were also observed. For instance, in Conference 13, the programme indicated that sessions were to be held online, despite the conference's location being listed as Rome. However, no participants from Italy attended; one session included representatives from only one country; and the same moderator chaired two sessions simultaneously, each featuring a different topic and a different set of participants.

The fictitious author also received expressions of gratitude and invitations to continue collaborating, despite having not attended the events. For instance, from Conference 9: "We look forward to new collaborations!" and from Conference 10: "We would like to express our sincere gratitude for your invaluable contribution. Our Scientific Committee is currently meticulously reviewing all the submissions to ensure that each paper meets the high standards of excellence that our conference upholds. We warmly extend an invitation to you to join us again in 2024, and we are enthusiastic about the prospect of your continued association with our academic community. Your participation and contributions are highly valued, and we look forward to fostering a long-lasting and fruitful academic partnership".

Absence or imitation of peer review

Peer review is the critical element that distinguishes a pseudoscientific conference from a legitimate one. All the analysed conferences claimed to peer-review the submissions, and all the 14 conferences held in Moldova indicated as much in their post-event reports, which are required for the scientific conferences to be officially recognized. In Conference 13 (allegedly held in Rome), the proceedings stated that "all applications have undergone a double-blind peer review process".

Out of the 16 conferences to which the manuscript had been submitted for publication, only 2 rejected it (conferences 15 and 16). The reasons cited for rejection included 'similarities with your previously published works', 'presentation at another scientific event', and 'not meeting the conference's requirements relevant to the conference'. However, none of these rejections referred to the results included in the text, which contained instances of plagiarism and had proposed a questionable index.

Of the remaining 14 conferences, 12 included the manuscript in their published proceedings. The contribution was published in the exact form as submitted by the author, without any comments, suggestions, or indications of peer review. Furthermore, some conference materials implicitly acknowledged that the contributions had undergone no substantive review or that the process was merely a formality. For instance, Conference 7 stated: "Authors are responsible for the accuracy of the material and the reliability of the presented facts". In the proceedings of Conference 9, only three reviewers were listed for 56 articles.

Two conferences did not include the manuscript in the proceedings and offered no explanation for the exclusion, although the

organizers had earlier issued certificates of attendance for the events. I emphasize that the fictitious author did not attend the conferences in question, and no one had presented the Timmy Index.

Conclusion

The analysed conferences did not conform to the classical definition of predatory conferences because they charged no participation fees and, therefore, sought no financial gains. However, the manner in which the conferences were conducted (lack of peer review and any discussion during the conferences) and the subsequent publication of an article that contained passages copied verbatim from another source and that proposed an absurd and universal index, with no scientific basis, for evaluating science led us to conclude that these conferences are distinctly pseudoscientific.

The present study represents a specific case in which the organization of low-quality conferences is not driven by financial gains but rather by the necessity to publish in order to meet reporting requirements, secure projects, obtain academic titles, or advance careers. The described situation could reflect a low level of scientific culture within the field of academic publishing and ignorance of the importance of validating scientific results through vetting by experts. It appears that there was a tacit understanding among various stakeholders – who participated in the organization of the 14 conferences – that form at least part of the national scientific research system to simulate scientific activity, the results of which are published in pseudoscientific channels—a conformist behaviour adopted by consensus within the academic community. Under these conditions, a publication culture emerges in these institutions whereby publishing becomes an end in itself,

rather than a means of disseminating research findings. Consequently, academia fosters a type of publication behaviour that prioritizes form over content, or mere dissemination of research outcomes over proper scientific enquiry.

The manner in which these conferences are conducted and the fact that these are some of the most important scientific events held by major universities in the country undermine the scientific evaluation process and foster an environment favourable for the proliferation of predatory pseudoscientific publications within the Moldovan academic community. Worse yet, local researchers from these universities may begin to consider it not only acceptable but even a norm to submit manuscripts to predatory publishers and conferences abroad, paying for rapid publication sans peer review and sometimes without any actual presentation at a conference.

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